

1 **Igsf receptors are actively expressed early in human development in utero.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of a
9 series of Igsf receptors that function in lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.
10 This included signature changes in expression of *Igsf8* and *Igsf21*.

11 Citations

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1. Li, Y., Wu, X., Sheng, C., Liu, H., Liu, H., Tang, Y., Liu, C., Ding, Q., Xie, B., Xiao, X. and Zheng, R., 2024. IGSF8 is an innate immune checkpoint and cancer immunotherapy target. *Cell*, 187(11), pp.2703-2716.